

Anomalous Migration of Anions to Cathode during Electrolysis

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If the anode side of a U-tube is carefully filled with a solution of dilute $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (or Na_2SO_4 or KCl) and the cathode side with water or dilute alkali, on continued electrolysis for overnight or longer at low current the anion is found to continually migrate to the cathode region until a steady state concentration differential (approx. 2:1) is attained in three to four days. If the current is switched off after a near-steady state is reached, this reverse migration continues and the two solutions intermix to a homogeneous state all throughout by overnight or so. This is impossible to happen by ordinary diffusion which is known to be inordinately slow. This kind of accelerated intermixing on switching off the current, called post-diffusion, is however inhibited if a little reducing agent (e.g., I^- ions or Fe^{2+} ions) or a few drops of concentrated electrolyte is added to the anolyte after switching off the current. It is theorised that static charge accumulates during electrolysis, positive for the anolyte, negative for the catholyte, which causes the unexpected reverse migration and post-diffusion and possibly also the anomalous features known as non-Faradaic electrolysis.

THE author^{1,2} as also Gosnell *et al*³ as well as Konya⁴ reported that under some conditions electrolysis of alkali metal sulphates or just water itself yields explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen both at the cathode as well as at the anode. This was termed non-Faradaic electrolysis. Evidently, in such cases some migration of the H^+ ions and the OH^- ions takes place in effect in the reverse direction. As an extension of the above work we report here some unexpected reverse migration of anions, which is easily observed using a very simple set-up.

Experimental

The experimental set-up is a simple U-tube (Fig. 1). We have used tubes of all sizes and also some other shapes with equally successful result but often tubes of about 30 mm O.D and 30 cm high with an inter-limb separation of about 4 cm. Our normal experimental procedure is to fill up the anode side (AB) with the electrolyte say, a dilute solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, and the cathode side (CB) with water as shown in Fig. 1. This is easily done by using two tight-fitting stoppers and a thin floating cork. First the mouth (C) is tightly stoppered and the dichromate solution is poured from the other mouth (A); it assumes the position AB. The mouth A is then tightly stoppered, B is opened and water (the lighter liquid) is poured with the help of a pipette slowly over a floating flat cork until CB is filled up. The stopper and the cork are removed and two electrodes are inserted. Electrolysis is now conducted by initially applying about 200 volts D.C. (we have often used D.C. mains of 220 volts) through two platinum foil (1 cm \times 1 cm) electrodes.

Fig. 1. A—Anode side ;
B—Boundary between acid and alkaline solution
C—Cathode side

The current naturally increases with time as alkali accumulates near the cathode. The current is kept in check with a rheostat in series and the final current is kept limited to 10 mA by adjusting the rheostat (with a potential drop of about 40 volts) to avoid the possibility of any heating.

It is expected that with progress of electrolysis brown chromic acid would collect near the anode and colourless alkali near the cathode. This is just

what happens during the first few hours of electrolysis; the anode region (AB) becomes brownish-orange; the cathode zone (CB) becomes alkaline and the boundary B becomes extremely sharp during this period. A totally unexpected thing however is observed on continuing the electrolysis. For example, using a dilute $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution (M/100 to M/250 is very suitable) and a maximum current set at 10 mA what happens is as follows. After an initial period of electrolysis for about six to ten hours or so, a faint yellow colour starts appearing over the cathode region (BC) indicating the presence of alkaline chromate ions. The yellow in BC region intensifies more and more on continued electrolysis, and by overnight the cathode solution (BC) becomes of fairly strong yellow colour. If the current is further continued this reverse migration becomes so strong that by the third or fourth day, a considerable portion (nearly one-third of the original) of the Cr(VI) is seen to have migrated to the cathode zone (CB). It is evident that there is a net movement of the Cr(VI)-anions from the anode zone to the cathode zone though the expected electrochemical migration is in the opposite direction.

That diffusion plays no part in the above observation is seen from the fact that a control experiment (i.e., without any current) shows hardly any diffusion on leaving undisturbed even for a few days, say weeks, except that the boundary becomes more and more diffuse with time. The above fact conclusively establishes that some conditions are created under the influence of the current which actuate the CrO_4^{2-} or $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ anions to migrate towards the cathode region.

The factors which are important for the above anomalous behaviour besides concentration are current strength and temperature. As to the effect of concentration this kind of reverse migration is seen under the same condition much earlier at lower concentration, M/100 to M/250 being more or less the optimum showing quite noticeable reverse migration by overnight. With M/25 or M/10 solution using the same 10 mA maximum current the yellow chromate colour round cathode hardly appears by overnight but quite distinctly only on the third day (M/25 > M/10). High temperature is helpful to anomalous migration. Higher current strength is only marginally helpful, if at all. Under a given condition of concentration, current strength and temperature, a final steady state is eventually reached in three to four days.

An interesting fact which probably has a bearing on the above observation is that starting with a dilute dichromate solution as the sole electrolyte all throughout the tube, a similar bi-coloured steady state with a sharp boundary (Brown/Yellow) is obtained on prolonged electrolysis and it is not possible to bring all the Cr(VI) anions to the anode chamber even on prolonging the electrolysis thereafter. It appears that a counterflow of the electrolyte

from the anode to the cathode sets in with progress of electrolysis, and this counterflow being in a direction opposite to the normal electrolytic migration of the coloured anion from the anode zone to the cathode zone, a steady state is finally reached.

This kind of reverse migration is somewhat accelerated if the cathode chamber is filled up with a suitable concentration of alkali instead of water to start with. It has been found that N/500 concentration of alkali gives quite satisfactory results. Using the set-up: Anode | $K_2Cr_2O_7$, M/100; N/500 NaOH | Cathode to start with and 10 mA constant current it is observed that fairly strong yellow colour accumulates in the cathode chamber by overnight and by the third day a steady state is reached with a concentration ratio of roughly 2 (Anolyte) : 1 (Catholyte) for Cr(VI) content. Dichromate has been used in the above experiment just because reverse migration is visually apparent in this case but almost all anions which do not get materially liberated on the anode show such behaviour. For example, if a N/100 Na_2SO_4 (or KCl) solution is electrolysed under the same condition as the anolyte (AB) and water as the catholyte (CB), a positive though faint test for sulphate ions (or chloride ions) is given by the catholyte by overnight which increases with progress of electrolysis to attain a similar steady state but with somewhat higher relative concentration in the cathode zone in about three days of continued electrolysis. This tendency of reverse migration of the anion is so strong that even if there is a constriction in the middle (i.e., the bottom of the U-tube being a few cm length of a narrow tube say 8-10 mm O.D); reverse migration still takes place with almost equal ease. Cations also show reverse migration under similar condition but at a somewhat slower rate, which we shall report in a separate publication.

Theory :

The classical idea of ionic migration is evidently inadequate to cover these anomalous facts. Some new idea has to be found. A rather simple explanation of the above puzzling fact lies in the idea that static charge collects in the anode zone and probably also in the cathode zone during the preliminary period of electrolysis. The anode zone (AB) gets positively charged and the cathode zone (CB) negatively charged, the former more so because of the high dielectric constant of water. This charge accumulation causes a bulk movement of the liquid due to the inherent tendency of a static charge to get dispersed. As a result a continuous intermixing between the catholyte and the anolyte takes place. This background intermixing is superimposed on the normal electrochemical migration of ions, as a result of which a net transport of Cr(VI) anions to the cathode zone is observed. This electrostatically caused reverse migration is probably also the cause of co-liberation in non-Faradaic electrolysis^{1,2}.

Some interesting observations may be cited in support of the proposed mechanism. The first one is the unexpected observation that such strong post-diffusion is also very strikingly seen if the current is switched off after the two-coloured solution is obtained on electrolysis of a dilute $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in a U-tube as described in a previous para; this electrostatically induced interdiffusion is so fast in this case that by overnight the whole U-tube becomes of practically homogeneous colour and pH all throughout as at the beginning. It should be realised that this is impossible to happen through the agency of ordinary diffusion which latter would have probably taken months to do similar homogenisation. Not only $K_2Cr_2O_7$ but also Na_2SO_4 and other similar salts show such accelerated diffusion induced by pre-electrolysis of a similar system (Anode | Na_2SO_4 N/100 : Water | Cathode).

Another interesting observation may be cited in support of the proposed mechanism. We argued that if positive charge is created in the anolyte this is essentially H_3O^+ which must be a highly oxidising agent and can be destroyed by adding a reducing agent. On adding a little KI solution or ferrous ammonium sulphate solution to the anolyte after switching off the current and letting it get mixed up by very careful stirring no more post-diffusion is observed; the yellow alkaline cathodic solution and the brown acidic anodic solution do not get mixed up even when left undisturbed for days which is just the same as the normal behaviour. Also, if two earthed wire gauges are dipped in the two limbs, the re-diffusion is found to be substantially

retarded but not fully inhibited as happens on adding Fe^{++} or I^- ions. It has been later found that a few drops of any strong salt solution also inhibits post-diffusion.

Thus, the electric current creates static charges, positive at the anolyte and probably also negative at the catholyte, more so the more dilute the solution, which in its turn cause an intermixing of the two solutions in the background superimposed on the normal electrochemical migration and this is the cause of the observed reverse migration. Incidentally, the author reported this surprising property of accelerated diffusion induced by pre-electrolysis which we now call post-diffusion in an earlier paper⁵ wherein no explanation was offered. This simple explanation based on known facts and principles appears to be capable of explaining the puzzling observation of reverse migration and post-diffusion and probably all aspects of non-Faradaic electrolysis.

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